

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

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June 30, 1979

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM: ACTIVITIES AND CONCERNS TO DATE

The first eight months of the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP) have been spent in identifying the concerned parties (LC, OCLC, RLG, WLN, SOLINET, individual libraries, the commercial sector, etc.), reviewing the literature and activities of the recent past in this area, and attempting to identify the most fruitful areas for the application of limited resources in pursuit of the program goals. The most obvious area for BSDP activity proved to be those concerns related to a bibliographic record service including data-base creation and control, communication between data bases, and standards pertaining to these issues. The BSDP is also turning its attention to the capacity of individual libraries to use the products of a bibliographic record service.

DATA BASES FOR A BIBLIOGRAPHIC RECORD SERVICE

Several activities have been started that relate to the data bases that will ultimately form the bibliographic record service. They are summarized below.

1. Data-Base Creation and Control.

It has been assumed that the MARC records that are produced and distributed by the Library of Congress (LC) will form the foundation for the bibliographic record service. It has also

been widely assumed that the records in the record service would be under some form of authority control. The authority control that exists over the LC MARC records is basically a manual system. All of these records, if used without alteration, can be considered under LC's authority control. Every bibliographic utility uses LC-generated MARC records; thus, to some extent each utility does use authority-controlled bibliographic records. If there is no utility-operated authority system, there is no guarantee that all other records in the data base would be under authority control. At the urging of the U.S. library community, LC makes portions of its internal authority files available to other libraries via computer tapes. But because only new authority records are being distributed, libraries do not have access to the retrospective authority records. LC has requested funds to support a project to make substantially all of the authority records used in the MARC data base available in machine-readable form as soon as possible. The proposal has received the strong support of the BSDP Program Committee.

Though an increasing number of LC authority records will become available in machine-readable form, the internal authority work continues to be a manual process. There is no functional, machine-based authority control system at LC. This contributes to the slow pace at which LC MARC records are made available to other libraries. LC has asked for systems-analysis assistance (three man-years) to help create an internal authority control system and make its authority records more rapidly available to other libraries. The BSDP Program Committee has discussed this proposal briefly and will soon discuss it in depth.

The CONSER data base (a bibliographic data base of serial records) has also been of concern to the BSDP. Under Title IIC of the Higher Education Act several libraries received funds to convert serial records to machine-readable form. Not all had initially considered using the CONSER data elements and format. Efforts are now underway to use the CONSER model to standardize these data conversion projects.

Additional questions are raised by the CONSER effort just described. To what extent should holdings be included in a national CONSER file? Should the holdings of all participating libraries be included? Or is there a strategy for recording selected holdings? Should holdings be included in the national file at all? The resolution of these issues will continue to be a BSDP concern.

2. Linking Bibliographic Data Bases.

One of the first interests of the BSDP was the exploration of linking the bibliographic utilities. It quickly became apparent that there was insufficient data on the economic, social, political, and service impacts of such links. To obtain such data, an RFP was prepared and sent to over 30 potential bidders. The RFP requires that a study be conducted in order to assess several possible methods for linking the utilities and to attempt to assess the economic, service, and social impacts. Bids are expected in the near future and it is likely that a contract will be let by September, 1979.

In the process of discussing various links and their special impacts on the utilities, the Research Libraries Group (RLG) and the Washington Library Network (WLN) concluded an agreement. The agreement involves the sharing of data bases and of system development and promises the exploration of a joint exportation package. Some of the questions related to linking may be resolved during joint RLG/WLN activities.

3. Nationwide Data-Base Design.

If various bibliographic data bases can be linked successfully, there must be a strategy that will lead to the nationwide availability of enough data bases to approach comprehensive coverage of available machine-readable bibliographic, authority, and location records. LC's Network Development Office (NDO) has long been working on this problem from a design perspective. A large number of research tasks have

been identified in the process of designing a nationwide bibliographic data base. Some of these tasks have been completed, others are just under way and still others have yet to be started. In concert with the BSDP Program Committee, NDO cooperated in a review by experts of the project. The results of the review verified that the approach taken by NDO was appropriate and rational. It also verified the underlying assumptions and, in the review process, identified some additional activities that would strengthen the project and its results. It is likely that the NDO project will be modified in light of the results of the review.

Once the project is complete and guidelines are available under which the several data bases can be searched as a relatively comprehensive set of bibliographic records, there still remains the question of who or what institution should direct and manage the access mechanism to these data bases. The system is unlikely to function well if there are several uncoordinated managers. Yet management of such a service may require forfeiture of certain prerogatives now claimed by database generators. Once a responsible party or organization is identified, the mechanism for providing access to the data bases can be more clearly defined. Part of this definition may flow from the results of the NDO project.

4. Standards for Bibliographic Records and Data Bases.

The keys to the concept of access to a variety of data bases are the standards which control the construction, content, and transmission of them. The BSDP has taken steps in several areas to promote the establishment of such standards.

Because AACR-2 (Anglo-American Cataloging Rules, second edition) did not prove to be a standard for the description of bibliographic entities (but it provides, rather, a set of options for their description), it has become necessary to select those options to be used in the machine environment in order to assure compatibility of various bibliographic data bases. The BSDP has

assumed a coordinating role in this area to see that the major stake-holders (bibliographic utilities and national libraries) participate in the selection of AACR-2 options. A Joint Committee on Bibliographic Standards established by the BSDP is the mechanism being used in this process. There still remain the very real problems of implementing AACR-2 within every U.S. library. It has not yet been determined whether the BSDP can or should play a role in facilitating that implementation.

A second standard of great interest to the BSDP is MARC -- the communication format for bibliographic records. The format grew out of the internal requirements of LC and incorporates a good many LC-specific features of little or no value to users of MARC tapes. Led by the concern expressed by LC's NDO, there is now under way with BSDP support - moral at this state since funding is from LC - a project to "inter-institutionalize" the MARC format. The intent is to remove the LC-specific elements from the format. Other substantive changes may or may not be considered in the review process.

The BSDP has from the first meeting of the Program Committee been interested in two other issues involving standards: a standard for an institutional identification code and a standard notation for detailed serials holdings. Elaine Woods has been commissioned to write a paper indicating the present state of affairs and how best to bring these two standards into being. It is likely that American National Standards Committee (ANSC) Z39 will take action on these issues.

There will be many other standards in the establishment of which the BSDP will be interested, for example, the NCLIS/NBS communications protocol for communication between computers at the applications level. This interest in standards requires an interest in the viability of ANSC Z39. Though the BSDP has not supported Z39 directly, the Council has contributed to the operational support of the committee for several years. A terminal grant for operational support has been offered.

Subsequent support will be related to specific standards work identified by the BSDP or other CLR programs.

Because our future - including our bibliographic future - cannot be insular, the interest in standards extends to the international level as well. The BSDP has supported on two occasions the travel expenses of U.S. representatives to international standards meetings. Though of modest fiscal impact on the BSDP, such support should continue in order to help assure international compatibility of communication formats, bibliographic records, and data bases.

USE OF THE PRODUCTS OF A BIBLIOGRAPHIC RECORD SERVICE

The emphasis of the BSDP so far has concentrated on issues related to data bases and the manner in which they might become collectively a bibliographic record service. The program must also address the other end of the spectrum - the individual library and its ability to use the products of this service.

1. Improved Performance at LC and the Utilities.

One of the concerns of individual libraries has been the delay between the time a bibliographic record is produced and the time it becomes available through one of the bibliographic utilities. The delay is a cumulative one with delay points in LC and the utilities. The LC delays are a function of internal systems and priorities. The LC processing system as noted above, is in the process of being upgraded; this should reduce a number of the delay points.

The transmission of the records from LC to the utilities is by U. S. mail with all attendant delays of that system. Until such time as LC is allowed to communicate with other institutions online, this delay is not really amenable to resolution. The process of seeking clearance for LC online activity is well advanced with a decision expected in the near term.

Delays at the utility level vary from one organization to another. However, with pressure from their users, the utilities seem committed to the most expeditious integration of new MARC records into their data bases as is economically feasible. BSDP concern is high in this area, but its activity has not gone beyond conversation.

2. Local Library Collection-Control Capacities.

The ultimate users of the products of a bibliographic record service are served by individual libraries. To assure that these products are appropriate to the needs of these users as well as the needs of local libraries, an assessment of requirements is needed. Flowing from the requirements should be one or more systems that are designed to use the products of the record service in response to user needs and the needs of rational library management. These systems are most likely to be focused on resolving collection control problems including circulation control, selection, acquisition, processing, collection management, collection use and preservation. The BSDP is interested in identifying a source for this kind of imaginative use of the products of the bibliographic record service. Of two proposals received in this area, one has now been rejected on the basis of narrow scope.

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Throughout the short life span of the BSDP, efforts have been made to communicate with a wide range of people about the activities and concerns of the program.

1. Program Committee.

Continuing communications on every effort within the BSDP flow through the Program Committee. The discussions at each meeting are summarized and distributed. Members, in turn, share these communications with their staff and often with their newsletter editors.

2. CLR Newsletter.

The CLR newsletter has been used to explain each major step in the program. Its wide distribution helps inform key people throughout the country.

3. Professional Journals.

News releases and articles have been distributed to a number of publications. The newsletters of the various regional networks have been particularly good at picking these up and publishing them. Major articles have been prepared for Library Journal and the Journal of Library Automation. Papers have been presented to a number of groups, the major one being ARL. A paper will shortly be prepared for ASIS.

4. LC's Network Advisory Committee/Network Forum.

The BSDP has from the beginning attempted to keep the members of the LC Network Advisory Committee (NAC) informed. NAC, officially an advisory committee to the Librarian of Congress, has had some identification problems since their advice has been so seldom sought. There is now a proposal to convert the Network Advisory Committee to a Network Forum. The membership would remain essentially the same, but the semiannual meetings would assume the character of a forum. That is, reports of network activities would be heard and discussed. In addition, a topic of significance would be addressed in a formal program with papers prepared and possibly distributed in advance. This focused discussion would result in a sense of purpose for the

membership and provide an extended consideration of the topic under discussion.

BSDP GOALS AND PRIORITIES

The goals of the BSDP have remained firm for some time now. They are:

1. Provide effective bibliographic services for all who need them.
2. Improve the quality of bibliographic products.
3. Provide purposeful control of costs of bibliographic processes in individual libraries.

The priorities of the BSDP are slowly but surely becoming more obvious. It is clear that a top priority is the provision of an authority-controlled data base of substantially all of the bibliographic records generated in the U.S. Thus, projects that most directly contribute to that reality should receive earliest attention. This data base will require sets of standards that the BSDP will continue to encourage.

Another priority that appears to grow in strength is the need to provide individual libraries with the capacity to use the products of a bibliographic record service. Consequently, projects that contribute most directly to that circumstance should receive early attention.

As the BSDP Program Committee continues to participate in the discussion of bibliographic issues, the priorities that will guide the BSDP in the coming months and years will crystallize. Even these priorities will change, however, in response to changing conditions and requirements of the U.S. library user and his libraries.

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BSDP EXPENSE REPORT

FOR THE PERIOD NOVEMBER 1, 1978 - JUNE 30, 1979

Grants		\$ 1,684
Contracts		8,934
Committee meeting expenses		
Project meetings		
February 5, 1979 - Message delivery system	\$2,568	
April 10, 1979 - Network advisory committee	3,262	
May 16-18, 1979 - LC Network Development Office review	7,149	
June 13-14, 1979 - Bibliographic standards	<u>1,984</u>	14,963
Program and Management Committee meetings		
November 16, 1978	1,499	
January 11, 1979	1,098	
February 23, 1979	585	
March 21, 1979	1,297	
April 11, 1979	826	
June 28, 1979	<u>69</u>	5,374
Director's expenses (salary, travel and other)		52,042
Staff travel		928
Consultants		100
Office expenses		<u>2,145</u>
		<u>\$86,170</u>

I certify that to the best of my knowledge and belief the above report is correct and that expenditures have been made in accordance with grant conditions.

Mary Agnes Thompson
Treasurer

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC. - BIBLIOGRAPHIC PROGRAM

TOTAL GRANT SUPPORT AND EXPENSE ALLOCATION

JUNE 30, 1979

	<u>Total Grant</u>	<u>Grant Term</u>	<u>1st Year Support</u>	<u>Expense Allocation % *</u>	<u>Expense Allocation</u>
Carnegie Corporation	600,000	3 yrs	200,000	15.1	13,012
Commonwealth Fund	150,000	3 yrs	50,000	3.8	3,274
Ford Foundation	750,000	5 yrs	150,000	11.4	9,823
Hewlett Foundation	300,000	3 yrs	100,000	7.6	6,549
Lilly Endowment	200,000	2 yrs	100,000	7.6	6,549
Mellon Foundation	600,000	yrs 4 & 5			
NEH/Mellon Foundation	1,800,000	3 yrs	600,000	45.4	39,121
Sloan Foundation	600,000	5 yrs	120,000	9.1	7,842
Totals	<u>\$5,000,000</u>		<u>\$1,320,000</u>	<u>100.0</u>	<u>\$86,170</u>

* Allocation is determined by the fraction using the grantor's annual support as the numerator and total annual support as the denominator.

Council On Library Resources, Inc.

THE YEAR 1978-1979

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Introductory Note

This report for the fiscal year ending June 30, 1979, has been prepared for the several foundations that provide general and/or program support to the Council on Library Resources, Inc. Included are an overview of current efforts, a summary of 1978/79 program highlights, and audited financial reports along with supplementary financial information. In addition, an interim report of the Bibliographic Service Development Program is attached. The annual report of the Council, which will incorporate much of the information in this report along with an indication of future program directions, will be published late in the year and copies will be forwarded when they become available.

Overview

The Council on Library Resources is an operating foundation that both funds and actively participates in activities related to the work of academic and research libraries and the interests of those they serve. Support for Council operations and programs is provided by a number of foundations. For the fiscal year 1979 these include: Carnegie Corporation of New York, the Commonwealth Fund, the Exxon Education Foundation, the Ford Foundation, the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, Inc., the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation.

The Council and its supporters are together an important element in a complex set of activities relating to the production, distribution, and use of recorded information. We would emphasize immediately that the Council is not working alone in this area. The Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, federal agencies, library organizations, some scholarly groups and publishers, to say nothing of many individuals, are all, to one extent or another, involved in what has quite suddenly become a most dynamic sector. The Council's special concern is with academic and research libraries because they are fundamental to the entire system. Their comprehensive collections, taken together, are a part of the foundation of our civilization; they provide for the information needs of many working scientists and scholars; and they are staffed by distinctively trained subject bibliographers, information specialists, and library administrators, all of whom contribute in important ways to the performance of libraries of all kinds.

The record of grants made during the past year and an account of activity in Council-administered projects constitute

the bulk of this report. As in past years, fellowships and internships have been awarded, support has continued for a few individual library programs and for certain general programs designed to improve library services and management, modest assistance has been provided for efforts related to standards development and collection preservation, and the extensive activity of recent years in automation and bibliographic activities has been substantially supplemented with additional funds and increased staff effort.

In short, the work of the Council and those it assists goes on. For those concerned with the well-being of libraries, the process of scholarly communication, the preservation of the human record, and a good many related enterprises, that work is important. And there are visible results to record. Many librarians have had a chance to widen their professional horizons. The comprehension and application of effective managerial techniques is more widespread in large libraries than it was a few years ago. More is known about the causes of paper deterioration. Standards that are essential to the application of computers to bibliographic operations have been set. Useful bibliographic products have been produced and some CLR-funded development work, especially in the area of computer applications, has begun to thrive in operating situations.

There has been and continues to be an unprecedented amount of activity in the library and information world today, but at times there seems to be no generally accepted and corresponding sense of direction. Occasionally, unduly competitive attitudes slow progress, redundant efforts tax limited financial and intellectual resources, access to bibliographic and substantive information is sometimes impeded rather than eased, and technology is misapplied. These and other indicators, however, suggest less that there is fundamental trouble in efforts to bring about improvement than they reflect the complexity and magnitude of the task of accommodating the reality of a revolution to an established set of activities that have evolved over the centuries since printing was invented. And, to the

careful observer, there are now visible some important new directions. The present confusion stems in large part from the fact that those directions are not yet completely developed or widely perceived. We are moving from a library-centered environment to a different sphere, one where each library is as much a means as an end. Computer and communications technology is making the change possible, and economic constraints (coupled with the sheer quantity of present and projected future publication) are increasing pressure to make change at an accelerated rate. The library catalog will be replaced by far more extensive bibliographic data bases. Some categories of information will never be published in the traditional sense but will be stored in computer memories and made directly available to users. Communications networks linking libraries to data banks will provide new products and services more closely tailored to the needs of individuals and groups. Improved management skills and better operating information, coupled with more sophisticated inter-institutional organizations and the prospect of new national resource collections will together create new possibilities for more effective collection control and simultaneously enhance overall access to information for library users.

"Utopia" will not come easily. Information has become a big and profitable business, and research library goals and means chosen to accomplish them are, at times, in conflict with the goals of others. Long-term objectives of universities and scholarship must be kept firmly in mind and the public interest case to extend access to recorded information worldwide, at acceptable costs and without constraint, must be pressed with skill and conviction by all who feel concern.

Put simply, we now sense where we are going -- getting there is the task facing CLR and the many others enlisted in the same cause.

PROGRAM HIGHLIGHTS

Bibliographic Services

A significant portion of Council activity has been devoted throughout the years to improving the means by which libraries and their users learn about what has been published, then locate and acquire desired items. Programs in this area have been national and international in scope. Through support of the judicious application of computer techniques to library processes, of cooperative cataloging programs, of the development of standards and other activities, the Council has sought ways to help libraries reduce unit costs of repetitive operations while improving their services. At the same time, the Council has attempted to encourage the development of nationwide services that will help all libraries and to foster the establishment of major components of a national library and information system.

Bibliographic Service Development Program

The principal event of the 1979 fiscal year was the beginning, in November 1978, of CLR's Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP). The program works toward the provision of effective bibliographic services that will meet the existing and future needs of scholarship and research, toward the improvement of bibliographic products, and toward the purposeful control of costs of bibliographic processes in individual libraries. Seven private foundations and the National Endowment for the Humanities are providing funds exceeding \$5,000,000 to support the CLR venture, which is projected to last at least five years.

CLR staff have spent the first eight months of program activity in identifying and bringing together the parties likely to be most concerned with bibliographic services, in reviewing

the literature and relevant activities of the recent past, and in identifying the most fruitful areas for the application of limited resources. Oversight for the effort is provided by a Management Committee, composed of Warren J. Haas, CLR President; William J. Welsh, Deputy Librarian of Congress; and Frederick H. Burkhardt, Past Chairman of the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science and Past President of the American Council of Learned Societies; and a Program Committee. Members of the latter group include Henriette Avram, Library of Congress; Carol Ishimoto, Harvard University; Frederick Kilgour, OCLC, Inc.; Edward Shaw, Research Libraries Group; and Roderick Swartz, Washington Library Network. In addition, BSDP program goals and concerns have been discussed by the Library of Congress' Network Advisory Committee, whose members, drawn from many information-related organizations, act as liaisons to their associations and represent organizational viewpoints.

From this crucible of discussion and study has been drawn a framework of action, which initially will concentrate on the creation of a bibliographic record service. Issues for consideration include data-base generation and control, communication between data bases, and promulgation of standards to facilitate information exchange. The BSDP planners are also turning their attention to the problems of individual libraries and their potential capacity to use the products of a nationwide bibliographic record service.

A variety of mechanisms are being used to develop suitable projects that hold promise of advancing BSDP goals. Grants will be made and contracts issued. Ad hoc committees and working groups are being appointed to focus on specific topics. Meetings and conferences are being held to allow for mutual investigation of problems and possible solutions. A broad spectrum of individuals, organizations, institutions, and agencies are being asked to contribute their knowledge and skills to the growing number of tasks necessary to the creation of the nationwide service.

Four grants or contracts were approved prior to June 30, 1979. One consultant reviewed the problems involved in linking bibliographic networks and prepared a request for proposal (RFP) that will result in a detailed assessment of the consequences and requirements of various linking and service options. A second consultant was employed to review the status of work toward establishing standard formats for institutional identification codes and bibliographic holdings notation. Travel grants will allow two U.S. librarians to represent U.S. interests abroad. One will participate in work to develop an international authority system and the other on the promulgation of an International Standard Bibliographic Description for analytic entries. Both efforts are coordinated by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions.

An example of an ad hoc committee is the Joint Committee on Bibliographic Standards, composed of technical experts from the major bibliographic utilities, research libraries, the Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, and CLR. At its first meeting in June 1979, the group embarked on an effort to assist in the selection of options provided under the new Anglo-American Cataloging Rules, second edition, for the machine-based bibliographic utility services in the U.S.

Another working group composed of various institutional representatives, staff members of LC's Network Development Office, CLR staff and consultants held an intensive three-day meeting in May 1979 to review the nationwide data-base design project under way at the Library of Congress' Network Development Office (NDO). They reviewed the research tasks, some of which have been completed, identified by NDO as necessary in the process of designing a nationwide bibliographic data base. The group verified that the NDO approach was appropriate and rational and suggested some additional activities that would strengthen the project and its results.

Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control

Jointly sponsored by CLR, the National Science Foundation (NSF), and the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS), the Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control was established in 1974 to identify and conduct certain activities that would lay the foundation for an improved national bibliographic system. The committee, whose six members represent the library, publishing, abstracting and indexing, information dissemination and allied communities, sponsored a workshop in October 1978 on issues surrounding methods for providing subject access to information. The resulting report and its recommendations for action was disseminated widely to library schools and major library and information organizations and was submitted to the Educational Resources Information Center (ERIC). The National Endowment for the Humanities also provided funds for the workshop.

At the time the committee was established, there was little purposeful planning at the national level toward developing a comprehensive system of bibliographic control. Because more formal mechanisms have since emerged, the committee determined that its activities should be terminated and that further meetings as a separate entity were unnecessary.

American National Standards Committee Z39

The American National Standards Committee Z39 (ANSC Z39) is one of several subject matter committees reporting to the American National Standards Institute, a national clearinghouse and coordinating agency for voluntary standards in the United States. ANSC Z39 is responsible for the development of standards relevant to information systems, products, and services as they relate to libraries, information services, and publishing. Further, Z39 is responsible for encouraging use of its standards in library, publishing, document delivery, information dissemination, and information and data handling systems.

CLR has supported ANSC Z39 since 1961. This past year two successive one-year grants to the committee's secretariat, the Council of National Library and Information Associations, Inc., brought the total CLR authorization for the committee to over \$216,000. NSF, NCLIS and OCLC, Inc. have also provided support. The committee is currently seeking support for its continuing program through contributions from member organizations, nonmember organizations, and federal agencies.

CONSER/COM

In September CLR awarded a grant of \$23,000 to the National Library of Canada (NLC) to enable NLC to publish, in computer output microfiche (COM), bibliographic records produced in the CONSER (Conversion of Serials) project. The CONSER project is a cooperative file-building effort initiated five years ago to develop a national data base of serials records. CLR funded and managed the project using the resources of 14 North American libraries and the on-line computer facilities of OCLC, Inc. OCLC has now assumed the management role. Production of CONSER/COM allows libraries that are not members of OCLC to have access to all the authenticated records in the CONSER file. As of June 30, 1979, NLC had received 93 subscriptions from 13 countries including Canada. The Library of Congress will begin distribution of CONSER microfiche in the U.S. early in the new fiscal year.

The Library of Congress is also taking steps to make the machine readable file of CONSER records available at nominal cost in the U.S. This file will be issued annually and will contain all authenticated and unauthenticated CONSER records.

Although CLR is no longer responsible for CONSER management, the Council still has great interest in the project, particularly as it relates to the overall development of national bibliographic control. In conjunction with the U.S. Office of Education, CLR has taken the initiative to organize meetings of CONSER participants and recipients of grants for retrospective

conversion of union lists of serials to machine-readable form. The grants were made under Title II-C of the Higher Education Act. The anticipated result of the meetings is the assurance that these discrete projects are more closely coordinated and compatible with the development of the national data base of serials records. This work is being carried out under the guidelines of the Council's Bibliographic Service Development Program, one element of which is national data-base construction.

Work on Non-Roman Alphabet at OCLC

CLR has joined with other funding agencies in supporting a program at OCLC to provide libraries with the capability for automated cataloging of materials in non-Roman alphabets. Since libraries currently catalog non-Roman materials manually, having such a capability will, it is hoped, improve access to such materials and help ameliorate processing costs. The work will be done in concert with the Library of Congress and others to ensure maximum usefulness to the library community as a whole.

Data-Processing Handbook

The first edition of Becker and Hayes' CLR-supported Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries was published in 1970. Royalties from this edition were used for a second edition, which appeared in 1974 and sold over 4,000 copies. In August 1978 Robert M. Hayes requested and received a CLR grant, which will make possible the preparation of a third, completely revised, edition. Emphasis in the new edition will be placed on providing an analysis of the actual experience in libraries in the development, evaluation, installation, and operation of computer-based systems. As in the past, the work will be published by John Wiley & Sons, Inc., and the Council will accumulate royalties to be used either for another edition or for related work.

Universal Bibliographic Control

If the Bibliographic Service Development Program is successful, a scenario such as this might develop: A library user in any public, academic, special, or school library, large or small, sits down at a computer terminal and within a few minutes locates several books and journal articles that bear directly on his or her current interest. The records through which the user sifts would have been generated in a variety of ways by a large number of agencies. Ideally, each record would have been generated only once and then shared by all who needed it. Library users would thereby have access to a record of nearly all of the publishing output of the nation.

If this concept of access, whether through machine-readable or manual means, is carried forward by other countries, then each nation will have established bibliographic control over its own publications and, if suitable standards are used, can share the resulting records with other nations. This concept is the basis of the program of the International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC), administered by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). The Council has supported this office, which is located within the British Library, since its establishment in 1974.

One of the UBC office's major activities is the promulgation, publication, and monitoring of use of the numerous International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions (ISBD). New descriptions currently in preparation include rules for preparing records of antiquarian materials, printed music, and analytics (i.e., journal articles, chapters in books, etc.). Acceptance of the ISBD's as standards will ensure uniformity in bibliographic records and facilitate their exchange across national boundaries. The office also acts as a secretariat to working groups and individuals engaged in special bibliographic projects, collects and disseminates information relating to bibliographic standards, coordinates meetings of national and international cataloging and bibliographic organizations, and edits and issues a variety of

publications on standards and other bibliographic matters. In addition to CLR support, the office receives income in the form of contributions from national library and cultural agencies, sales of publications, and UNESCO contracts.

Library Operations and Services

Over the years the Council has supported a number of projects devoted to helping libraries operate more efficiently and serve their constituencies more effectively. The Council has approached this area of its program in a variety of ways. A series of grants, for example, have gone to academic libraries for experimental programs involving joint planning by library and teaching faculty of ways to integrate the library more closely with the educational process. Another group of programs has focused on improving library management. Support has also been given to other associations that are in turn attempting to assist member libraries to improve the conduct of their daily business. Management, operations, and services are so closely interrelated that it is impossible to assist in one area without affecting others. They are parts of a continuum that must be seen as a whole.

Academic Library Program

The central effort of the past year is the Academic Library Program administered by the Office of Management Studies (OMS) of the Association of Research Libraries (ARL), and funded by CLR (drawing on Carnegie Corporation fund), the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, and ARL itself. The OMS has been funded by the Council since 1970 and has applied a kind of self-help methodology to library operations through such programs as the Management Review and Analysis Program, the Academic Library Development Program, and the Collection Analysis Project. These programs provide guidance in the form of manuals, procedures, and

personal consultation to academic libraries to help them examine themselves, analyze their operations, identify strengths and weaknesses, and outline areas and methods for change.

All academic libraries in the United States are eligible to participate in the Academic Library Program. A modest fiscal commitment, estimated at \$4,000 - \$7,000, is required to participate. A Small Library Planning Project, supported by the Lilly Endowment, will allow six libraries in Indiana to begin self-studies in the fall of 1979. On the drawing board are a Services Development Program and a Community and Two-Year College study.

The five-year project will be advanced by the training of up to 100 librarians as consultants to assist libraries in conducting their self-investigations. During the year the ALP Advisory Committee, on which a CLR staff member participates, established procedures for the selection of consultant-trainees. Applicants were sought in early 1979 for the first Consultation Skills Workshop to be held in October. As of May 31, 251 applications had been received, and regional interviews were scheduled for the month of August. OMS plans to train about 20 persons each year.

Final Awards Under College Library Program

In the fall of 1978, the final awards to be made under the College Library Program, jointly sponsored by CLR and the National Endowment for the Humanities, were announced. The three awards bring to 35 the number of institutions that have participated in the program since its genesis in 1969. Each institution has designed activities to enhance the library's role in the educational process. Teaching faculty, administrators, librarians, and, in some cases, students have assisted in the formulation of each project. The institutions are required to share in program costs by providing at least 25 percent of the total budget from funds over and above the regular library budget.

Two of the institutions, Lake Forest College in Illinois and Tusculum College in Tennessee, will expand instructional programs begun with grants from CLR's Library Service Enhancement Program (no longer operating). A required sophomore humanities course is the foundation of the Tusculum program, while Lake Forest will use computerized data bases as primary instructional tools. The third grantee, Franklin and Marshall College in Pennsylvania, plans to implement a comprehensive library instruction program in support of eight areas of the curriculum in the humanities and historical studies.

As announced at the close of Fiscal 1978, CLR and NEH have decided to discontinue the College Library Program and no new applications will be accepted. It is planned that the new Academic Library Program (see above) will incorporate the experience and expertise of persons who have participated in the College Library Program.

IFLA's Professional Programs

The Council has awarded a new grant of \$75,000 to the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) to enable the organization to develop further its professional programs. The grant is the fourth CLR award to IFLA for the work of its general secretariat. Total CLR support since 1971 amounts to \$439,000.

IFLA's expansion of its professional activities began in 1976 following a restructuring of the association. The revised statutes created a professional organization composed of divisions by type of library, by library activity, and by region. Within the divisions are 35 sections and round tables that engage the energies of school, public, special, academic, and national librarians from 106 countries.

To coordinate the programs and projects of the diverse groups, IFLA created a professional board and hired a deputy secretary-general. In addition to acting as secretary to the

professional board and coordinating divisional and sectional programs, the deputy secretary-general has worked in recent months to expand IFLA's links with the Arab world and with French- and English-speaking Africa. The deputy will also act as secretary to a new program management committee, which will direct and coordinate the work of IFLA's programs for universal bibliographic control, universal availability of publications, and international MARC. Formation of the new committee was approved by the IFLA Executive Board in May, 1979; it will become effective on September 1.

IFLA has had consultative status with UNESCO for many years and has provided an important international forum for the discussion of library problems. In addition to Council funding, IFLA receives income from membership dues, sales of publications, conference proceeds, UNESCO grants and contracts, the Dutch government, and the Canadian International Development Agency.

Microform Service Development

The past fiscal year brought to a close a CLR grant to Princeton University as part of Princeton's Microform Service Development Program. Grants from the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and the Xerox Corporation were used to replace worn equipment, improve the microforms facilities, reduce cataloging arrearages and complete analytical cataloging of microform sets. The CLR grant, awarded in July 1976, was used to support training of division staff, improve graphics, develop an orientation program for other library staff and students, and hold a regional seminar for microforms librarians from other libraries. The project's final report pointed to an increase in the use of the Microform Division in 1977-78. Over 15,800 persons had used over 44,000 items.

Library Resources and Their Preservation

As inflation has eaten away the purchasing power of library budgets, the need to preserve the resources at hand has become even more critical. Replacement costs, whenever available, are high, and new materials are rising in price. Even the most self-sufficient libraries are beginning to listen to the lyrics of resource-sharing tunes sung with increasing frequency by their less-well-off neighbors. More purposeful collection building combined with a well-planned preservation program appears to be the theme song of the future.

Preservation has always been high on the list of Council priorities, although CLR has not been able to support preservation programs or collection development at individual libraries. A December 1976 National Preservation Program Planning Conference, called by the Library of Congress and supported with a CLR grant, identified a variety of needs that were reiterated in a recent Library Journal article: "professional training of conservators and continuing education for librarians; model organizational approaches; discovery of safe 'minor repairs' to be performed by nonconservators; expanded cooperative programs for the sharing of scarce expertise; development of an ethic or philosophy to relate technical operations responsibly to the 'value' of materials; effective and economical mass treatment of deteriorated materials," etc. A continuing series in the journal is now exploring these and other issues in an attempt to focus attention and provide factual data on aspects of the preservation problem.

Collection building is equally important and numerous questions require an analytic approach. Assessing the concept of "national collections," understanding better the relationship between proximity of materials and their use, and improving methods for assessing collection strength are only a few of the issues of importance that must be addressed. Specific action to

be taken in the future is not yet certain, but the past year has seen some progress in several areas. A small step was taken when a CLR grant was awarded to support a summer 1979 conference of book selection officers from academic libraries to discuss the problem of retrospective collection development.

National Periodicals Center

Last year's report described the preparation by Council staff of the 256-page A National Periodicals Center Technical Development Plan (Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, 1978). Although the Council's official role in this effort was concluded when the report was turned over to the Library of Congress early in the present report year, CLR staff received numerous requests to explain the intent of the plan and its meaning to library users, scholars, the business information community, publishers, and other concerned citizens. Program staff therefore prepared a slide show illustrating the concept of an NPC that was presented at meetings and conferences sponsored by library and information organizations around the country.

A number of scholarly and educational organizations have endorsed the concept of a National Periodicals Center. As this report year closed, the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science's Advisory Committee on a National Periodicals System had commissioned a group broadly representative of interested constituencies to prepare draft legislation.

Preservation and Paper

CLR and the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation invited about twenty individuals with knowledge of paper manufacturing, publishing, and library book preservation programs to contribute to a May 14, 1979, discussion in New York. The participants sought to gather information about book paper and its use and to identify ways to address prospective aspects of the collection preservation problem.

The participants focused on current practices in the manufacture of paper and its use for books and journals. Examples of questions raised were: Is book paper that meets reasonable specifications for permanence and durability readily available in sufficient variety and at acceptable cost? If appropriate paper is available, why is it not more generally or universally used for publication of books and journals? If not, or if other obstacles exist, what action is required, and by whom?

At the conclusion of the discussion, those present encouraged the continued pursuit of issues identified and formed a committee, under the direction of Herbert S. Bailey, Jr., of the Princeton University Press. The committee will propose procedures for identifying preservation objectives and options for action, recommend ways to arrive at acceptable standards, and attempt to extend understanding and wider recognition of the preservation problem itself. CLR has set aside a small sum to support the activities of the committee.

National Shelflist Measurement Project

The University of California, Berkeley, has published a compilation of statistical data on the holdings of 27 research libraries, including the Library of Congress. The report's preparation was supported by a CLR grant awarded in January 1978. Entitled "Titles Classified by the Library of Congress Classification: National Shelflist Count," the 64-page report represents the third phase in a study of the distribution of holdings among research libraries undertaken by the Chief Collection Development Officers of Large Research Libraries. The project director believes that the project "provides the beginnings of a national program for the evaluation and coordination of research library collections."

Collection Development Using Books for College Libraries

In 1977, CLR provided a small grant to Stockton State College in Pomona, New Jersey, to experiment with the machine-readable tapes used to produce the second edition of Books for College Libraries. CLR had assisted the preparation of both first and second editions of the work. The second edition, published in 1975 by the American Library Association, is a catalog of the 40,000 basic titles any four-year liberal arts college should have in its library if it intends to provide students with an adequate education.

Stockton maintains a machine-readable listing of its own collection. The college used the ALA tapes to compare its holdings and generate lists that could be used for evaluation, for purchasing, and for circulation studies. To encourage other small libraries that lack sophisticated programming staff, Stockton successfully employed an information sciences student to prepare the programs. Stockton used the services of the New Jersey Educational Computing Network to complete the project.

Professional Education and Training

How can academic libraries attract the highly qualified people needed to carry out the libraries' missions of service to scholarship and teaching? More important, how can academic libraries retain competent staff and build in them the skills necessary to provide, with their peers, leadership in higher education management? And even more fundamental, how can the profession as a whole recruit the most well-qualified individuals to its ranks and keep them there? The Council has sought to provide some answers in terms of programs that provide for staff development and focus on increasing the knowledge and skills of professional library staff members. Three programs were active in this fiscal year. But the conviction persists that the

broader topic of basic professional education for academic and research libraries needs more concentrated attention.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

As in former years, the Council selected highly qualified individuals to participate in its Academic Library Management Intern Program. The program is designed to create a pool of highly qualified library managers who will be ready and able to move into senior administrative slots as these become vacant in future years. For the 1979-80 academic year, two women were chosen, each to work with the director and top administrative staff of one of the country's important academic libraries selected for its recognized administrative excellence. Each intern receives a stipend equal to her normal salary and benefits (up to \$25,000). Rebecca D. Dixon, director of the Library Services Division of the Center for the Study of Youth Development, Boys Town, Nebraska, will intern with Jay K. Lucker, director of libraries at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT); while Susan K. Nutter, associate head of the Engineering Libraries at MIT, will intern with James F. Govan, director of the University of North Carolina library.

Following a review of the program, it was determined that the period of internship would be reduced to ten months for the 1980-81 academic year. Council advisors agreed that the shortened period would not significantly dilute the experience and would free funds for additional internships. Up to five interns will be chosen for the seventh year of the program.

Although no guarantees can be made in terms of career advancement, former interns now hold such responsible positions as university librarian at Canada's McMaster University, director of the J. Hugh Jackson Business Library at Stanford, assistant librarian for general reader services at Princeton, and director of the central library at Joint University Libraries in Nashville.

Health Sciences Library Management Intern Programs

Like its predecessor above, the Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program is designed to increase the number of librarians who, in addition to having the intellect, personality, and character required for director-level positions, also have a firm grounding in management processes and techniques. The program is funded by the National Library of Medicine (NLM) and administered by the Council.

Three women emerged successfully from a field of 19 applicants for the 1979-80 academic year. June E. Bandemer, assistant director of the Falk Library of the Health Professions, University of Pittsburgh, will intern with C.K. Huang, director of the Health Sciences Library, State University of New York at Buffalo. Eleanor Goodchild, director of library services at the Los Angeles County Harbor General Hospital, will work with Richard A. Lyders, executive director of the Houston Academy of Medicine, Texas Medical Center Library. Finally, Leonoor S. Ingraham, coordinator of collection development and head of public services at the Health Sciences Library, University of Oregon, will intern with Gerald S. Oppenheimer, director of the University of Washington Health Sciences Library.

Health Sciences Interns receive stipends (up to \$25,000) that cover their basic salary and benefits. In addition to working with the director of a major academic health sciences library, interns will spend two weeks at the National Library of Medicine.

CLR Fellowship Program

The oldest of the Council's professional development programs, the CLR Fellowship Program, was suspended this year following the selection of ten fellows for the 1979-80 academic year. In the eleven years of the program, 215 fellowships have been awarded. Thus far, they have produced nearly 80 journal articles and at least 15 books and occasional papers. Some

fellows have used the opportunity to improve their technical and administrative skills through short-term internships or work experiences. Others have shared their research in conference programs or applied their new skills to the improvement of their current work situations. It should be noted that, while the annual awards program has been suspended, the Council continues to entertain research proposals from individuals throughout the year.

The recipients of the awards and their projects in the final round of the program follow.

Judith S. Braunagel, assistant professor, SUNY at Buffalo Library School, and Rao Aluri, research assistant, OCLC, Inc. To compile a guide to U.S. government scientific and technical information sources.

Boyd Childress, periodicals librarian, Western Kentucky University. To study the history and development of the libraries of the eight state universities in the South from 1860 to 1880 in order to determine their relationship to parent institutions.

Sheila D. Creth, assistant director, University of Connecticut Library. To investigate current approaches and methodologies in the area of manpower planning and job analysis as reflected in selected academic libraries and private industry.

George S. Grossman, director of the Law Library, University of Minnesota. To study the historical development of legal literature and legal research tools in England.

William E. Hannaford, Jr., acquisitions librarian, Middlebury College. To study collection development in ten small college libraries.

Mary E. Pensyl, head, NASIC Search Service, Massachusetts Institute of Technology. To study the impact of user demands on the reference departments of academic and research libraries that have offered online bibliographic services for several years.

Anne B. Piternick, professor, School of Librarianship, University of British Columbia. To investigate sources of support for bibliographic activities in the United States with emphasis on public and private funding and the economics of publishing.

Patricia Ann Polansky, Russian bibliographer, University of Hawaii. To work for three months at the Scott Polar Research Institute in Cambridge, England, and to attend the 14th Pacific Science Congress.

Suzanne Striedieck, chief, Serials Department, Pennsylvania State University. To study the effectiveness of technical services operations from the point of view of general reference librarians.

Research and Analysis

In 1956, the first major CLR project involved a series of studies aimed at developing "targets for research in library work." A series of 18 studies evolved under the direction of Ralph R. Shaw, and the resulting multi-volume set was published by Rutgers University under the title The State of the Library Art. The project developed under the guidance of a group of experts, which included not only librarians but also "library-problem-minded persons drawn from natural science, scientific instrumentation and business-machine work."

Council interest in sponsoring research has not waned in the intervening years. But it has been a long time since CLR has defined a structured, formal approach. An organized program of

research would, of course, touch on all areas of Council interest, such as bibliographic control, collection development, and library management. It might well be broader in focus, looking at the heart of information processes, at how society uses information, and how the transfer of information can be most effectively accomplished for the general good. It might well be narrower, taking a creative approach to specific library processes, to defining the relationships between libraries, publishers, jobbers, indexers, and other sectors of the information community.

In the past year, the Council has discussed these ideas with a number of consultants and interested persons. Although a definite program in this area has yet to be organized, CLR has responded to research proposals on an individual basis and will continue this practice in the future.

New Edition of British Library Resources

Robert B. Downs, Dean of Library Administration Emeritus, University of Illinois, will prepare a second edition of his British Library Resources with the aid of a small CLR grant awarded this year. The first edition, published in 1974 by the American Library Association and Mansell of London, has nearly sold out in Britain. Dr. Downs will use the grant to travel to Britain in the fall of 1979 and plans to complete the manuscript in mid-1980.

Academic Library Leaders

The Council has awarded a grant of \$10,000 to Wayne A. Wiegand, assistant professor in the College of Library Science, University of Kentucky, to edit a series of essays to be entitled "Leaders in American Academic Librarianship, 1925-1975." Such well-known figures as William Dix, Keyes Metcalf, Robert Vosper, Louis Round Wilson, and Herman Fussler will be among the twelve to fifteen influential academic librarians to be included. Some of the essays will be published in future issues of The Journal

of Academic Librarianship prior to their collective appearance as a monograph.

Future Role of Public Libraries

In 1976 and again in 1977, CLR awarded funds to the National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries for research activities in preparation for the White House Conference on Libraries and Information Services. A series of background papers were prepared and the first, Career and Employment Information Services, was received by the Council in April. In addition, on behalf of the committee Doubleday published a 189-page volume entitled For the People: Fighting for Public Libraries (New York, 1979). In the words of the preface, the volume "seeks to help citizens understand how the public library got to be what it is today, the vital role the public library plays in the life of the nation, and how it can assist in the nation's future growth and prosperity."

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

July 1, 1978 - June 30, 1979

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1

Mr. Kempner was elected to succeed Dr. Davis at the November 1978 annual meeting.

2

Elected at the November 1978 annual meeting.

3

Until August 15, 1978.

4

As of June 18, 1979.

5

Formerly Information and Publications Officer, Ms. Gwinn became Program Officer on January 23, 1979.

6

As of November 1, 1978.

7

Until September 29, 1978.

8

As of November 29, 1978.

9

Until her retirement, June 30, 1979.

10

Until January 19, 1979.

Publications Resulting From
CLR-Supported Programs and Fellowships

1978 - 1979

Part 1: Programs

Anglo-American Cataloging Rules. 2d ed. Chicago: American Library Association, 1978.

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- No. 46. Planning for the Future of the Card Catalog.
- No. 47. Automated Cataloging.
- No. 48. External Fund-Raising.
- No. 49. The Use of Annual Reports.
- No. 50. Fringe Benefits in ARL Libraries.
- No. 51. Professional Development.
- No. 52. Cost Studies and Fiscal Planning.
- No. 53. Performance Appraisal.
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- Bruntjen, Scott. "Librarians in a Time of Uncertainty." (July 1978)
- Gunning, Kathleen. "Increasing the Reference Librarian's Participation in the Research Process." (September 1978)
- Mathews, William D. "A Siege of Committees." (November 1978)
- Sherby, Louise S. "Academic Librarian: Librarian or Faculty Member." (November 1978)
- Stevens, Norman D. "A Hard Look at Reserve." (May 1978)
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Council on Library Resources Inc.

GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND CLR-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS
ACTIVE IN FISCAL 1979GRANTS

FY 1979

	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/79
American Association of Law Libraries, Chicago, Illinois Survey of U.S. and Canadian law library resources (\$20,000-1968)	\$ 2,000	\$ -0-	\$ 1,000	\$ 1,000
American Library Association, Chicago, Illinois Ethnic and sexual composition/salary survey for librarians (\$13,856-1977)	11,856	-0-	4,928	6,928
Secretariat for the U.S. National Committee for the UNESCO General Information Program (USNC/UNESCO-PGI) (\$2,500-1978)	2,500	-0-	765	1,735
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C. Academic Library Program (326,500-1978)	326,500	-0-	58,500	268,000
Office of University Library Management Studies (\$81,136-1974; \$210,000-1975)	23,000	-0-	23,000	-0-
Bibliothèque Royale Albert Ier, Brussels. Preparation of Belgian exhibit (\$2,000-1978)	2,000	(2,000)	-0-	-0-

FY 1979

	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/79
Council of National Library & Information Associations, Inc. Haverford, Pennsylvania Continued support of the American National Standards Institute Com- mittee Z-39 through 9/79 through 9/80	-0- -0-	\$20,000 30,000	\$20,000 -0-	-0- \$30,000
Robert B. Downs, Urbana, Illinois <u>British Library Resources</u> Second edition	-0-	3,000	-0-	\$ 3,000
Earlham College, Richmond, Indiana Periodical list for <u>Choice</u> (\$7,500-1975)	\$ 4,200	-0-	1,000	3,200
Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, Michigan Project LOEX (\$41,969-1975; \$4,765-1977)	1,265	(298)	967	-0-
International Council on Archives, Washington, D.C. ICA Secretariat (\$72,000- 1975)	6,000	(2,230)	3,770	-0-
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, The Hague, Netherlands. Professional activities of the secretariat (\$174,000-1975) through 2/79 through 2/81	45,014 -0-	(14) 75,000	45,000 9,000	-0- 66,000
International Office for Uni- versal Bibliographic Control (\$70,000-1974; \$144,200-1975; \$150,000-1977)	121,756	-0-	50,000	71,75
Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa. Mechanized indexing procedures applied to production of sub- ject-enhanced keyword index (\$1,926-1977)	426	-0-	-0-	42

	FY 1979			
	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/79
Library of Congress, Washington, D.C.				
COMARC project (\$106,132-1975)	\$21,483	\$ (8,983)	\$ 12,500	-0-
Meeting on MARC format for AACR 2 (\$5,843-1978)	5,843	805	4,632	\$ 2,016
National Preservation Program, meetings of Ad Hoc Advisory Committee (\$5,960-1977)	4,819	(4,819)	-0-	-0-
Use of the ISSN by the U.S. Postal Service (\$14,231-1978)	8,231	-0-	8,231	-0-
MIDLNET, Green Bay, Wisconsin Toward salary of a techni- cal advisor (\$22,778-1977)	17,778	-0-	-0-	17,778
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Office for Advance- ment of Public Negro Colleges, Atlanta, Georgia Status report on libraries of black public colleges (\$4,000-1978)	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
National Endowment for the Hu- manities, Washington, D.C.				
Continuation of College Library Program (matching grant)	-0-	41,058 (261)	41,058 (261)	-0-
National Library of Canada, Ottawa Production of a computer output microform (COM) microfiche service listing authenticated bibliographic records created in the CONSER project	-0-	23,000	23,000	-0-
The New York Public Library, New York, on behalf of the National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries Research on future role of public libraries in preparation for White House Conference on Libraries and Information Ser- vices (\$15,000-1978)	15,000	-0-	14,579	421

	FY 1979			Unpaid 6/30/79
	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
OCLC, Inc., Columbus, Ohio. Development of Non-Roman alphabet capability for library processes	-0-	\$15,000	\$15,000	-0-
Organization of American States, Washington, D.C. Travel report production costs of meeting to approve MARCAL (\$12,000-1976)	\$6,525	(5,682)	843	-0-
Princeton University, Princeton, New Jersey Microform service development (\$10,000-1976)	8,750	(3,160)	5,590	-0-
Carl M. Spaulding, Sunnyvale, California Travel grant to chair meetings of new standards group, the Library Committee of National Micrographics Association	-0-	2,000	442	\$1,558
State University of New York/Binghamton Meeting on Retrospective Collection Development	-0-	2,675	-0-	2,675
Stockton State College, Pomona, New Jersey Innovative use of Books for Col- lege Libraries II (\$5,150-1977)	3,150	-0-	3,150	-0-
Syracuse University, Syracuse, New York Improved subject access to books by augmentation of MARC records (\$76,615-1976; \$6,958-1977)	6,573	(2,515)	4,058	-0-
University of California, Berkeley. National shelflist measurement project (\$20,000-1978)	5,000	-0-	-0-	5,000
University of California, Los Angeles Third edition of Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries	-0-	14,500	2,500	12,000
University of Connecticut, Storrs New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar (\$20,610-1976)	9,943	-0-	7,017	2,926

	FY 1979			
	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/78
University of Kentucky, Lexington "Leaders in American Academic Librarianship, 1925-75"	-0-	10,000	-0-	10,000
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill Administration of ANSI Com- mittee Z-39 Through June 1978 (\$23,719- 1976)	11,219	(1,194)	10,025	-0-
Total grants	\$ 671,831	\$237,038 (31,156)	\$370,555 (261)	\$507,419

COUNCIL ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	<u>FY 1979</u>			
	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/79
<u>Academic Library Development Program</u>				
Carnegie-Mellon University (\$21,000-1977)	\$ 3,000	\$ (1,266)	\$ 1,734	-0-
Drew University (\$18,845 -1977)	3,645	-0-	3,645	-0-
North Carolina Central University; for project coordinator (\$73,527-1977)	7,957	(6,096)	1,861	-0-
Seattle University (\$15,510 - 1978)	10,760	-0-	9,500	\$1,260
University of Wisconsin- Parkside (\$21,350-1977)	12,350	(1,270)	11,080	-0-
	<u>37,712</u>	<u>(8,632)</u>	<u>27,820</u>	<u>1,260</u>
<u>Academic Library Management Intern Program</u>				
1977-78 (\$98,330-1977)				
Graham R. Hill	458	(3)	455	-0-
Jo Nell Hintner	5,021	234	5,255	-0-
Jordan Scepanski	4,499	(56)	4,443	-0-
J. Daniel Vann, III	4,833	-0-	4,833	-0-
	<u>14,811</u>	<u>234</u>	<u>14,986</u>	<u>-0-</u>
		(59)		
1978-79 (\$65,000-1978)				
Sandra Coleman	21,807	-0-	20,687	1,120
Joan Chambers	21,807	-0-	21,028	779
Sara C. Heitshu	21,386	-0-	20,634	752
	<u>65,000</u>		<u>62,349</u>	<u>2,651</u>
1979 - 80				
Rebecca D. Dixon	-0-	29,000	-0-	29,000
Susan K. Nutter	-0-	29,000	-0-	29,000
		<u>58,000</u>		<u>58,000</u>

	FY 1979			Unpaid 6/30/79
	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Advanced Study Program for Librarians				
1977-78 (\$73,092-1977)				
Joan M. Bechtel	1,933	(1,791)	142	-0-
Jane Benson	2,632	(1,744)	888	-0-
George C. Hart	2,377	(2,377)	-0-	-0-
Beth J. Shapiro	4,067	(4,067)	-0-	-0-
	<u>11,009</u>	<u>(9,979)</u>	<u>1,030</u>	
Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP)				
Davis B. McCarn, Rockville Maryland - *Preparation of Request for Proposal	-0-	6,434	434	6,000
Saine W. Woods, Arlington, Virginia Position Paper on Standards *	-0-	2,500	-0-	2,500
Library of Congress, Washington, D.C. Travel grant for U. S. Represent- ative - Copenhagen meeting on an International Authority System	-0-	1,105	-0-	1,105
Chemical Abstracts Service, Columbus, Ohio Partial support for U.S. repre- sentative at ISBD(AN) meeting in Sweden	-0-	579	-0-	579
		<u>10,618</u>	<u>434</u>	<u>10,184</u>
ONSER Project (\$250,000-1975)	42,773	(35,223)	7,550	-0-

* Contract

	FY 1979			
	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/79
Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program				
1978-79				
Carol Jenkins	-0-	\$26,951	\$25,408	\$1,543
William E. Maina	-0-	27,400	17,432	9,968
Faith A. Meakin	-0-	<u>29,400</u>	<u>19,759</u>	<u>9,641</u>
		<u>83,751</u>	<u>62,599</u>	<u>21,152</u>
1979 - 80				
June E. Bandemer	-0-	27,485	-0-	27,485
Eleanor Goodchild	-0-	31,000	-0-	31,000
Leonor S. Ingraham	-0-	<u>28,245</u>	-0-	<u>28,245</u>
		<u>86,730</u>		<u>86,730</u>
Library Service Enhancement Program				
1977-78 (\$194,857-1977)				
Beloit College Beloit, Wisconsin	\$ 3,432	(1,416)	2,400 (384)	-0-
The Colorado College Colorado Springs, Co.	3,021	(2,554)	467	-0-
Georgia Southern College Statesboro, Georgia	4,550	(1,138)	3,412	-0-
Georgia State University Atlanta, Georgia	2,107	(85)	2,022	-0-
Glenville State College Glenville, West Virginia	1,280	(1,280)	-0-	-0-
Hampton Institute Hampton, Virginia	4,492	-0-	2,750	1,742
Joint University Libraries Nashville, Tennessee	1,430	(2,934)	(1,504)	-0-
Lake Forest College Lake Forest, Illinois	2,415	-0-	2,415	-0-

FY 1979

	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/79
Tusculum College Greenville, Tennessee	108	-0-	108	-0-
University of Colorado Colorado Springs, Colorado	1,738	(1,770)	(32)	-0-
University of Kansas Kansas City, Missouri	5,801	(1,474)	4,327	-0-
Wayne State University Detroit, Michigan	<u>12,378</u>	<u>(3,712)</u>	<u>8,666</u>	<u>-0-</u>
	<u>42,752</u>	<u>(16,363)</u>	<u>26,567</u>	<u>1,742</u>
		<u>(1,920)</u>	<u>(1,920)</u>	
Total Council-administered Projects	<u>214,057</u>	<u>239,333</u>	<u>203,335</u>	<u>181,719</u>
		<u>(70,256)</u>	<u>(1,920)</u>	

FELLOWSHIPS

FY 1979

	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/79
Walter C. Allen, Associate Professor, Graduate School of Library Science, Uni- versity of Illinois	\$ 255	(255)	\$ -0-	\$ -0-
Virginia M. Bowden, Assoc. Director, University of Tex. Health Science Center Li- brary, San Antonio, Texas	4,500	868	4,400	968
Judith S. Braunagel, Asst. Prof., SUNY at Buffalo Li- brary School, and Rao Aluri, Research Asst., OCLC, Inc. Columbus, OCLC, Inc., Columbus, Ohio	-0-	1,594	-0-	1,594
Carolyn P. Brown, Chief, Information Services, Na- tional Bureau of Standards	214	(99)	115	-0-
John D. Byrum, Jr., Catalog Librarian, Princeton Uni- versity	1,460	(1,460)	-0-	-0-
Lois Mai Chan, Assoc. Prof., College of Library Science, University of Kentucky	990	(334)	656	-0-
Boyd Childress, Periodicals Librarian, Western Kentucky University	-0-	3,370	-0-	3,370
Jay B. Clark, Chief of Tech- nical Services, Houston Public Library	2,138	-0-	1,500	638
Sheila D. Creth, Asst. Director, University of Connecticut Library	-0-	2,890	-0-	2,890

	FY 1979			Unpaid 6/30/79
	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Florence K. Doksansky, Asst. Librarian, Rotch Library, MIT	753	(165)	588	-0-
Josephine R. Fang, Prof., School of Library Science, Simmons College	250	(21)	229	-0-
Wayne Gossage, Library Direc- tor, Bank Street College of Education, New York City	3,040	-0-	-0-	3,040
George S. Grossman, Dir. of the Law Library, University of Minnesota	-0-	3,150	-0-	3,150
William E. Hannaford, Jr., Acquisitions Librarian, Middlebury College	-0-	1,220	300	920
Robert W. Karrow, Jr., Cur- ator of Maps, Newberry Library	885	(332)	553	-0-
Mark Kovacic, Gifts and Exchange Librarian, Penn. State Univ.	160	(171)	(11)	-0-
Hugo Kunoff, Subj. Librarian for Modern Languages, Indiana University	1,870	(932)	938	-0-
Frederick C. Lynden, Asst. Chief, Acquisitions Dept., Stanford Univ. Libraries	560	(286)	274	-0-
Mary D. McFeely, Head, Reference Department, Smith College Library	3,557	-0-	3,000	557
Dorothy A. Pearson, Serials Librarian, Princeton Univ.	2,097	-0-	1,500	597
Mary E. Pensyl, Head, NASIC Search Service, MIT	-0-	2,760	-0-	2,760

	FY 1979			Unpaid 6/30/79
	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Anne B. Piternick, Prof., School of Librarianship, University of British Columbia	-0-	2,735	-0-	2,735
Patricia Ann Polansky, Russian Bibliographer, University of Hawaii	-0-	2,680	1,930	750
Alvis H. Price, Associate Library Personnel Officer, UCLA	495	(495)	-0-	-0-
W. Boyd Rayward, Asst. Prof., Graduate Library School, University of Chicago	3,524	-0-	2,400	1,124
Shiro Saito, Assoc. Univ. Librarian for Pub. Services, University of Hawaii	2,325	(109)	2,216	-0-
St. Anne Striedieck, Chief, Serials Department, Penn- sylvania State University	-0-	3,170	-0-	3,170
Jean F. Trumbore, Assoc. Reference Librarian, University of Delaware	832	(211)	621	-0-
Sheh Wong, Head, East Asian Library, Univ. of Minn.	335	-0-	335	-0-
Total Fellowships	<u>\$30,240</u>	<u>\$24,437</u> <u>(4,870)</u>	<u>\$21,555</u> <u>(11)</u>	<u>\$28,263</u>

FY 1979

	Unpaid 6/30/78	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/79
<u>SUMMARY</u>				
Grants (page 5)	\$671,831	\$237,038 (31,156)	\$370,555 (261)	\$507,419
Council-Administered Projects (page 9)	214,057	239,333 (70,256)	203,335 (1,920)	181,719
Fellowships (page 10)	30,240	24,437 (4,870)	21,555 (11)	28,263
	<u>\$916,128</u>	<u>\$500,808</u> <u>(106,282)</u>	<u>\$595,445</u> <u>(2,192)</u>	<u>\$717,401</u>